

Disabled Women's Experiences at the Workplace: Evidence from Kabul Based Organizations

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Abstract

In the recent years, attentions are brought to the situation of those people, who are most deprived section of society like women with disabilities. Women with disabilities are facing many types of discriminations because of their gender and secondly because they are disabled. They are economically dependent on others even for their basic necessities of their life. They are discriminated in the recruitment process and they are ignored to be hired for higher positions. As we live in 21st century of equality and still disabled women treatment at workplace is not as it should be. So this study identifies the relationship of various factors effecting disabled women at workplace. Quantitative method is used and data was collected through five point Likert scale. The study concludes that independent variables (Discrimination, Performance of disabled women and Policies & Procedures) have significant effect on disabled women at workplace.

JEL Classification: I0, K4, M1

Keywords: Afghanistan, Disabled women, workplace, discrimination

1. Introduction:

In the recent years, disability has become a chronic issue for most of the countries especially the developing nations, as they are dependent on other members of society. They are vulnerable to most of diseases due to fewer facilities provided to them. The reasons of low attention for disabilities are given as below:

- Society looked upon them down, due to discriminations and exclusion.
- Sexually and disability related wrong believe or myths which exist in the world
- Lack of special awareness programs about disability.

- Organizations whether public and private have less consideration on employing disabled women and men.
- In most of the regions in north side, preference related to sex and race in employment exist.

The recent statistics by World Health Organization 2010, around 10% of the world population are living with disabilities, majority of them are living in developing countries. It is believed that causes of disabilities are accidents, being victims of violence and existing of natural defects. In most of societies people do not believe on disabled women and men capabilities and abilities and they are not provided any chance to work, and they think that people with disabilities can't perform the task like the normal people.

1.1 Problem Statement

Women with disabilities are not provided special working facilities inside the organizations, as most of business owners have fear from higher costs which they have to incur because of a disabled individual. Moreover, there is not special scheme related to support financially women with disabilities, and government of Afghanistan is not implementing or supporting programs which improve situation of women with disabilities. Furthermore, there are wrong believes about female working performances, as they are not able to work efficiently in the organization. These are the main challenges which they are facing mostly related to their business activities. (Nayak B, 2013) The data from National Disability survey in Afghanistan shows that, 70 percent of people with a disability aged over 15 years are unemployed; 53 percent of males and 97 percent of females. In comparison, 25 percent of men and 94 percent of women without disability are unemployed, Also, women and girls with disability are especially afflicted by discrimination and abuse; firstly as persons with disabilities, but also as women. This also indicates that, based on an estimated population of 25 million people, there are between 747,500 and 867,100 persons with severe disabilities in Afghanistan, of whom approximately 17 percent are war disabled (126,000 to 146,000). Between 52,000 and 60,000 people are landmine survivors;

about 6.8 percent of the total number of people with disabilities (Francois Trani.J.&, Bakhshi P.,&, Ashraf M.(NDSA), 2005).

1.2 Research Question

In order to mitigate above mentioned issues, this study focused to answer below listed question:

What is the relationship between women with disability and their experience at the workplace?

1.3 Objective of Study

To identify the relationship between disability and experience of women at workplace - Kabul based organizations.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Existence of discrimination in the workplace

A research conducted in India, to find out about violence against women with disability, targeting 15 disabled women who had been victim of violence, through open ended interview. The study was found out that most of them had not been aware from their impairment, then in the elder ages due to emphasize from their counterparts, they had started different feelings related to them. Those people having visionary problems were provided helps inside the schools; in contrary those with locomotors impairments were much more isolated. Some of them argued that they were not provided the chance to be enrolled in the educational institutions. Moreover, women had the wrong feeling that they are not accepted, first due to their gender differences and second because of their disabilities. Most of them reported that they had the experience of being beaten by the school teachers and inside the house. In the same way, some of the parents had provided the chance for their daughters not having the feeling of isolated. Furthermore they have experienced different type of sexual harassment. Women's experiences of domestic violence included emotional and verbal insults, withholding money, threats of abandonment or physical violence, and actual physical violence. The most vulnerable women seemed to

be those who were married off at an early age by parents who no longer wanted to take responsibility for them or were concerned about their ineligibility as wives. Physical challenges and perceptions of women with disability as defenseless made them easy targets. Verbal and physical sexual harassment by strangers occurred in public spaces, trains, and buses (Daruwalla. N, 2013).

2.2 Existing Views related to the Performance of disabled women

Research done about challenges of healthcare of women with disabilities taking the evidence from Indonesia, it was found out that disabled women are the most deprived group in Indonesia, less studies has been conducted on health issues, due to this there is a gap for those in policy making positions. The result shows that still people with disabilities especially women are the most marginalized group of people in provision of health care services. It was approved as well that, wrong perception in society will no work as a hindrance to their efforts for the independence, however those who have accepted their disabilities were prone to social, economic, educational and health services dependency and they faced many challenges. To improve their situation government has implemented effective programs for their support in health care services, this was as a result of activists working in this regards. This is recommended that, to change the behavior of people in society which is possible through organizing special awareness programs in educational centers as they are connected almost with all population in one region and indirectly they can influence on other members of the family, Secondly, the government also need to prepare environment for their participation in most of the health care services and business activities. (Laroche 2017)

2.3 Existence of specific policies and procedures for the disabled women

The finding from survey on disabled women shows that, they are provided low level jobs, disclosure of hidden disability result in change in their partner's behaviors and providing any type of mental care services are the privilege provided for them.

Though situation of disabled people in the public sectors is better than working in private sectors, however they are still prone to different types of discrimination, and special policies are required to target participation of women with disabilities in both sectors, and encouraging providing high ranking position for them, and providing special accommodation to support them (Hirst, Thornton and Dearey 2004).

2.4 Existing Views related to the Performance of disabled women

The fact is women's movement is controlled by non-disabled women and disabled women lack the confidence and ability to raise their voice. Although the Persons with Disability Act have been initiated since 1995 in India, it has failed to bring about any desired change in the life of women with disability. Lot of modifications and amendments are required time to time as per the changes. On the basis of the findings of this research, it is recommended that; firstly some mandatory number should be fixed for all organizations to recruit employees having some sorts of disabilities, both for private and public sectors. Secondly, members of the family of women with disabilities need to be consulted, to provide enough support for those in need. Special schemes need to be in place to protect pregnant women, to reduce possibilities of birth of any child with disabilities. Some special programs need to be implemented to support entire life of disabled women such as pension funds. Furthermore, special measures are required to protect disabled women against any type of violence (Nayak 2013).

2.5 Conceptual Framework

Source: Authors Compilation

To find out the result of the study it is required to find out relationships among variables and statistically measure them. On the basis of each relation who is considered on hypothesis can be build. Dependent variable is the

main core of study which changes on the basis of change on independent variables. In the below the variables are provided as:

Dependent Variable

- Experience of women with Disability in the Workplace

Independent Variables

- Existence of discrimination in the workplace
- Existence of specific policies and procedures for the disabled women
- Existing Views related to the Performance of disabled women:

3. Hypothesis

First Hypothesis

H₀: Discrimination has not positive relation on experience of disabled women. H₁: Discrimination has positive relation with experience of disabled women

Second Hypothesis

H₀: Existence of specific policies and procedures for disabled women has not positive relation on experience of disabled women

H₁: Existence of specific policies and procedures for disabled women has positive relation with experience of disabled women

Third Hypothesis

H₀: Existing Views related to the Performance of disabled women has not positive relation on perception and experience of disabled women

H₁: Existing Views related to the Performance of disabled women has positive relation on experience of disabled women.

4. Research Methodology

4.1 Methodology

This is the process which is used to collect specific information for the purpose of making proper decision in organization about a study, here the method of data collection, types of data, population taken into consideration for study, sample from population, methods and data which are used.

In this research both qualitative and quantitative data is used from both primary and secondary data types. The secondary are those studies which

already done, by various international and national agencies working in this field and primary data is collected through specific questionnaire. To find out relationship among variables, statistical measures such as frequency analysis, linear regression and correlation is used through SPSS software application.

4.2: Method of Data Collection

In this research primary data is collected through questionnaires submitted to the employees with disabilities and secondary data is collected from international journals, books and other researches or study conducted in the national level.

4.3: Sample Size and Population

Sample of 100 females with disabilities are considered using from random method of sampling. The questionnaire would be distributed and data would be collected and analyzed in SPSS. Statistical measures such as frequency analysis, regression and correlations are used to analyze the data and find out specific results.

5. Analysis and Findings

5.1: Analysis of Data:

This is the most important part of research which helps to find out the result of data. Different methods and measures are available which the researcher may use. Statistical measures have been helpful for the centuries as they are used to analyze information. In this study as well, measures of central tendency, measures of dispersion, and measure of correlation, regression and principle components methods are used to find the result of data. In the following each part is discussed:

5.2: Reliability Test

To measure reliability or internal consistency of data used in this study, Cronbach's Alpha test is used. If the result of this measure is significant, it means the data are measuring what it was planned in the first place. The standards which is given for this measure is as below:

Table 1: Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.610	.534	20

Source: Output generated from SPSS

The table shows that the result of Cronbach's Alpha test is greater than 0.6, as per the rule the variables have inter-consistency with one another.

5.3: Normality Test

This is the test which measure how data is distributed, whether normal or not. In this measure the null hypothesis is considered that data is normally distributed in the study. In this method if the significant value is greater than 0.05, then the null hypothesis is selected, otherwise the alternative hypothesis would be chosen.

Null Hypothesis:

- There is not difference between normal distribution and data taken as sample

Alternative Hypothesis:

- There is difference between normal distribution and data taken as sample

Table 2: Test of Normality

	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	Df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
DiscriminationIntheWOrkPlace	.122	100	.056	.967	100	.070
PoliciesRelatedTowomenwithDisabilities	.121	100	.061	.967	100	.090
ExistingVeivsRelatedTowomenWithDisabilities	.104	100	.010	.979	100	.121
a. Lilliefors Significance Correction						

Source: Output generated from SPSS

The significant value more than 0.05, then the data are normally distributed, and in case its value is less than 0.05; it means the data are not normally distributed. In the above table the significant values for Shapiro-Wilk measure are more than 0.05, which means data are normally distributed.

5.4.: Measures of Central Tendency

A single value is the result of application of this statistical measure, which shows how data are differentiated, grouped or arranged in comparison to value which exists in the center. In this category mode, mean and median are included.

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics

		Discrimination In the Work Place	Policies Related To women with Disabilities	Existing Views Related To women With Disabilities
N	Valid	100	100	100
	Missing	0	0	0
Mean		15.0400	15.5900	17.0800
Median		15.0000	16.0000	17.0000
Std. Deviation		2.45328	2.67836	3.17401
Variance		6.019	7.174	10.074
Skewness		-.169	-.480	-.158
Range		12.00	13.00	14.00

Source: Output generated from SPSS

Mean: The mean value for the first variable which is discrimination in the workplace is 15.04 and for the existing view related to performance of disabled women it is 17.04, which is highest in comparison to others.

Median: The lowest median value is 15 which is for the variable discrimination in the workplace and the highest median value is 17 for the variable of existing views related to the performance of disabled women.

Standard Deviation: The lowest value is for the first variable and the amount of standard deviation is high for the variable existing views related to performance of disabled women which its value is 3.7 and this means data related to this variable is more dispersed than other two variables.

Variance: In the above table amount of dispersion is higher for the variable existing views related to performance of disable women as its value is 10.7 and the lowest amount of variance exist for the value of first variable (Discrimination in the workplace) with the value of 7 which is low in comparison to the last one.

Skewness: This show asymmetry of a data, the result of this measure can be positive or negative. In case the result is positive, it means the data are skewed to the right from the mean value and vise versus. In the above table the result of Skewness for all variables are negative, which means all data are skewed to the right.

5.5: Correlation Analysis

This table specifies how two variables have mutual relation with one another. The changes in one variable will cause the changes in another variable.

Table 4: Correlations

		Discrimination In the Work Place	Policies Related to women with Disabilities	Existing Views Related To women With Disabilities	Experience of Women With Disabilities
Discrimination In the Work Place	Pearson Correlation	1	.279**	.043	.658**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.005	.491	.000
	N	100	100	100	100
Policies Related To women with Disabilities	Pearson Correlation	.279**	1	-.3	.646**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.005		.993	.000
	N	100	100	100	100
Existing Views Related To women With Disabilities	Pearson Correlation	.070	-.001	1	.595**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.491	.993		.000
	N	100	100	100	100

Experience of Women With Disabilities	Pearson Correlation	.658**	.646**	.595**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	
	N	100	100	100	100
**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).					

Source: Output generated from SPSS

In the above table to compare correlation of independent variables, this is clear that (Discrimination in the workplace) has highest correlation with the dependent variable, as its value is 0.658 which is more than other two variables. It means one unit changes in the mentioned independent variable, the dependent variable changes by 0.658 units. Moreover correlation coefficient among independent variable (policies related to disabled women) and dependent variable is 0.64, this means due to one unit changes in the independent variable will cause change of 0.64 units to dependent variable. Furthermore correlation among existing views related to the performance of disabled women and dependent variable is 0.5, which is the lowest value in comparison to other variables. While other variables (existing views about performance of women) and policies related to disabled women have negative correlation having value of -0.3, which means increase in the amount of one variable will result in reduction in the value of another variable

5.6: Regression Analysis

5.6.1: Model Summary

The researcher in this section is concerned about the r-square and adjusted r square. The values of both factors are provided in the following table.

Table 5: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change

1	.989 ^a	.979	.978	203.50719	.979	1494.715	3	96	.000
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a. Predictors: (Constant), Existing Views Related To women With Disabilities, Policies Related To women with Disabilities, Discrimination In the WorkPlace

Source: Output generated from SPSS

R square shows how much the data or the responses are dispersed from the regression line. The result of R^2 lies between (0-100), any responses closer to 100, means data responses are not very much deviated and this is good sign. However it is important to note that, the result should not be 100, which becomes the actual line of regression and is meaningless. In another term which is called Adjusted R^2 , the variation percentage is adjusted to the number of observations; this is an important measure when there are number of predictors. In the above table amount of R-square is 0.979, and amount of adjusted r- square is 0.978, which shows data is not deviated from one another.

5.6.2: ANOVA Table

This shows the variables are significantly fit. In the following table this is shown that amount of Sig is 0.000^b which shows data are significantly fit the model.

Table 6: ANOVA

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	185711598.850	3	61903866.283	1494.715	.000 ^b
	Residual	3975856.940	96	41415.176		
	Total	189687455.790	99			

a. Dependent Variable: Experience of Women With Disabilities

b. Predictors: (Constant), Existing Views Related To women With Disabilities, Policies Related To women with Disabilities, Discrimination In the Workplace

Source: Output generated from SPSS

5.6.3: Coefficient

Table 7: Coefficient

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-8314.833	185.742		-44.766	.000
	Discrimination In the work- place	268.421	8.706	.476	30.833	.000
	Policies Related To women with Disabilities	265.271	7.955	.513	33.348	.000
	Existing Views Related To women With Disabilities	245.204	6.461	.562	37.951	.000
a. Dependent Variable: Experience of Women With Disabilities						

Source: Output generated from SPSS

The researcher is concerned about beta and t-ratio and the descriptions are provided as below:

Beta(B): This is the measure which shows how much independent variable has impact on dependent variable, if the amount of beta is high, the level of impact of independent variable on dependent variable would be high as well, and vice versus. The above table it is depicted that the variable (existing view about performance of women with disabilities) has higher value as it is 0.65, which shows any unit changes in the amount of mentioned variable will bring changes of 0.65 on dependent variable. However beta values for other two variables (discrimination in the workplace & policies related to women with disabilities) are 0.4 and 0.51 respectively, which shows in comparison to other one, their impact on dependent variables are low. This is also mentionable that all factors have positive impact on dependent variables.

T-Ratio: In the above table the values of t-ratios, all of them are higher than 2, and this means all alternative hypothesis are selected. In simple sentence each variable (discrimination in the workplace, policies related to disabled women and existing views related to disabled women) has positive impact on the experience of women with disabilities.

6. Conclusion and Recommendations

6.1 Conclusion

Disabled women are from the most deprived section of people living

on the earth. They are witnessing different types of problems in the family, in organizations in lower section and overall society as a whole. In the family they are regarded as incapable of practicing their rights, due to that they are departed from their basic rights, and they are not regarded human as others. In organizations they are not employed in the first instance and if they are employed, they are not provided equal chance of improvements, trainings and other chances of promotions and they are not provided the chance of being employed in the high ranking positions as well. Furthermore, in the whole society as well, people do not trust the abilities, capabilities and skills of employees, due to that they are not allowed or not given the chance to live like other humans.

The result of this study shows that people with disabilities, especially women are facing different types of discrimination from the beginning of employment process, after selection and even in the organizations. They are not employed because of their disability, if they are employed they are not provided the chance of promotion and attending the training programs and those without disabilities are given the chance. In most of the countries such as Afghanistan, employers are not giving equal chance for disabled people, as it is hard for the country to find out employment opportunities for healthy people, and it is unimaginable to think about employment of disabled people in the organizations. Moreover, governments are required to have specific policies for the improvement of lives of those who are somehow apart from the other parts of society. This is obvious, any country which has experience of more than three decades of war, the number of casualties and disabled people are higher than others with no existence of war. Afghanistan also had the same experience, and there is large number of people living here. The government has specific policies for this section, but unfortunately on the basis of the result of this research this has been found out that, the government is not providing special awareness about the policies and most of people are not aware and are not using from the privileges provided to them. The only part of which most of the people knew that is the educational preference provided to them. Furthermore, this is

hard to believe that in an environment which discriminations exist and most of people do not have any information about disabled people rights, people have positive view about the performance of disabled women. Most of respondents replied that people with disabilities have not the capability of performing the tasks as efficient as others, and some of the individuals have positively responded and regarded disabled women as capable as other people.

6.2: Recommendations

The result of this study shows that all factors such as discrimination, policies related to disabled women and existing views about disabled women had positive relation on experience women with disabilities. It means if discrimination is improved and no one is discriminated in the working environment, then number of disabled women will have much more intention to work. In the same way as many policies are specific and for the welfare of people with disabilities, the organizations would experience higher number of participants to receive the services specialized for them. Moreover, one of the measure of development is considered Human Development Index, if the country wants to improve the situation of the people with disabilities the following recommendations are necessary to be taken into considerations:

- The government should pass specific policies to encourage equal participation of disabled people especially women, in the work environment.
- There is need for specific policies for the welfare of disabled people, and also the government should target most of rural areas to spread awareness programs, to aware them about the rights and privileges specialized for them.
- Education facilities are from the most important factor which play a vital role for the improvement of people with disabilities, but as far as the respondents argued, there are not specific facilities for them in the rural areas, the government or other international agencies are required to work in the improvement of people.
- People with disabilities can also play an important role to change their situation and use from the services which are provided by the government.

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